

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING TERMS TO FIRST AND SECOND GRADERS IN READING CLASSES

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Annotation

This article outlines new ways to teach terminology in reading classes to students in the elementary grades, revealing the importance of incorporating terms into the student's speech.

Keywords: vocabulary of terms, vocabulary of terms, beginner class, students, speech, style of speech, types of speech, speech of students, education.

МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ТЕРМИНАМ ПЕРВОКЛАССНИКОВ И ВТОРОКЛАССНИКОВ НА УРОКАХ ЧТЕНИЯ

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Аннотация

В данной статье показаны новые способы обучения младших школьников терминам на уроках чтения, раскрыта важность включения терминов в речь учащегося.

Ключевые слова: термины, словарь терминов, начальный класс, учащиеся, речь, стиль речи, типы речи, речь учащихся, образование.

Education gives creative activity to the spirituality of the people of Uzbekistan. All the best opportunities of the growing young generation are

manifested in it, their profession and skills are continuously improved, the wise advice and experiences of the older generations are highly understood and passed on to the young, mature generation.

Uzbek terminology is the main source for elucidating the history of the Uzbek language and some of its unclear issues. Studying terms has both scientific and practical importance. The study of terms is of great help in determining the phonetic, lexical, grammatical, stylistic and synonymic norms of the language, as well as in the moderation of orthography and spelling.

Prof. about Uzbek terminology. U. Tursunov's thoughts are also important for our linguistics today. K.M. Musayev compares terminology as the lexicon of the language to a city. According to him, although the terminology is built on the basis of a single plan, it is not built at once. It is formed on the basis of historical conditions, various architects, designers, inventors of different generations participate in its creation. They build every building they are building with good research. The specific complexity of terminology regulation is determined by this.

In elementary school, not only do students' imaginations and understandings expand, but their imaginations and understandings fill and define. As soon as the child comes to school, a change occurs in his existence, his social status develops in the basic sense, and educational activities that are important and leading for him are formed. As a result of educational activities, specific basic young psychological conditions begin to develop. Education becomes the nucleus of action that develops their mental abilities and consciousness. Thus, concepts become a function of knowledge, knowledge becomes a function of skills, and skills become a function of progress.

Elementary school students are not able to speak words, express their opinion, and tell the probability of occurrence of the happening event and its reasons. Qualities such as the ability to discuss, justify and defend an event or process, and self-confidence are formed as a product of special educational

activities. Logical thinking, the ability to imagine situations without visual aids, and the understanding of certain laws that occur are the main conditions for mastering educational materials from subjects. That's why we need to teach our students an adequate approach to studying nature, to simplicity, to a deeper understanding of the laws of the macro and micro world of all the processes taking place in nature.

Creation of terminological dictionaries, that is, terminology is an integral part of general lexicography, although most of the processes in them are similar to each other, but there are also many differences between them. In particular, the classification and definition of terms is quite different from the classification and definition of words in the general literary language.

In a number of articles, the relationship between common words and terms, terminology and nomenclature, their common and different aspects, specific features of general philological dictionaries and terminological dictionaries, and the presentation of certain field terms in an explanatory dictionary are mentioned.

References

1. .A.Karimov."O'zbekistonning o'z istiqlol va taraqqiyoti yo'li".Toshkent,"O'zbekiston" nashriyoti,1994 yil,78-sahifa
2. "Xalq ta'limi" O'zbekiston respublikasi xalq ta'limi vazirligining ilmiy-metodik jurnali. 2016 4-son (iyul-avgust)
3. Madvaliyev A. O'zbek tilida kimyo terminlari va ularning izohli lug'atda berilishi. O'zbek tili va adabiyoti. 2008-yil, 5-son.